

Documenting the Languages of the People of the Center, especially Bora and Ocaina (North West Amazon): Final Report

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Title of the project	Documenting the Languages of the People of the Center, especially Bora and Ocaina (North West Amazon)
Project investigators and cooperation partners	<p><u>Principal investigators:</u> Frank Seifart (project coordinator) (2004-2007: Ruhr-Universität Bochum, 2007-2009: Universität Regensburg) Doris Fagua (Universidad Nacional de Colombia / Université Paris 7) Jürg Gasché (IIAP, Peru / CNRS, Paris (-2005)) Nikolaus Himmelmann (2004-2007: Ruhr-Universität Bochum, 2007-2009: Universität Münster)</p> <p><u>Affiliated investigator:</u> Juan Alvaro Echeverri (Universidad Nacional de Colombia)</p> <p><u>Institutional cooperation partners:</u> Instituto de Investigaciones de la Amazonia Peruana (IIAP, Iquitos) FECONA (association of indigenous communities of the Ampiyacu river, Peru)</p>

Narrative part of the report

Abstract in English

This project documented the highly endangered languages of the so-called People of the Center, a culturally relatively uniform, but linguistically diverse group in the North West Amazon. We documented the traditional cultural practices, including memorized ritual discourses lasting up to three hours, repertoires of thousands of songs, and drum communication systems derived from the individual languages, as well as the informal use of the languages on a daily basis, which are both nowadays rapidly declining in a process of transculturalization towards national society and language shift towards local Spanish.

Three of the seven mutually unintelligible and in part genetically unrelated languages, Bora, Ocaina, and Witoto, were the subject of exemplary and comprehensive documentations, consisting of fully transcribed and translated video recordings of a representative sample of each major type of communicative event. A number of older Witoto recordings of types of ritual speech no longer practiced today were processed and integrated in the current documentation. In addition, extensive data were included from the moribund Resígaro language, which now has only two speakers. We also processed and included substantial data from the now extinct Nonuya that were collected in the 1970s-1990s.

The corpus consists of over 2000 individual recording sessions with a total of over 350 hours of video and/or audio recordings. Each session is placed under a thematic node in the DOBES archive, together with a metadata description, which specifies its contents, participants, etc. Almost 700 of these sessions were transcribed and translated into Spanish, adding up to an electronically searchable online corpus of over 230,000 words. Additionally we created and uploaded an extensive apparatus (almost 180 pages), which provides important information about the languages and culture of the People of the Centre, facilitating future use of the data by anyone not familiar with these.

We also collected specific data for a variety of possible analyses, including anthropological, linguistic, psycholinguistic, and ethnobotanical and -zoological analyses, and have already carried out ourselves analyses relating to linguistic anthropology, grammatical description, and historical and contact linguistics. From our data, we also produced a number of materials specifically for language revitalization purposes, including teaching materials and 56 DVDs with bilingual subtitles. A language documentation server was installed in Iquitos, Peru, which hosts a copy of our documentation and constitutes a new centre for language documentation in Peru, and is part of a Latin American network we initiated.

A PhD dissertation project carried out in the project, a descriptive grammar of Ocaina, is close to completion. We also helped to establish language documentation at German universities through teaching. A number of follow-up projects and activities, both in Latin America and Europe, are on their way, including the elaboration of further teaching materials and typological studies based on language documentation corpora.

Abstract in German

Dieses Projekt dokumentiert die stark bedrohten Sprachen der so genannten People of the Center, einer kulturell relativ einheitlichen, aber sprachlich heterogenen Gruppe im Nordwest-Amazonas. Es dokumentiert sowohl die traditionellen kulturellen Praktiken, z.B. auswendig gelernte rituelle Diskurse von bis zu drei Stunden Länge, Repertoires von Tausenden von Liedern und

Trommelkommunikationssysteme, als auch den informellen, alltäglichen Gebrauch der Sprachen. Beides nimmt heutzutage rapide ab durch Transkulturation hin zur nationalen Gesellschaft und Sprachwechsel zu lokalem Spanisch.

Drei der sieben gegenseitig unverständlichen und zum Teil genetisch nicht verwandten Sprachen, Bora, Ocaina und Witoto, wurden in exemplarischen und umfassenden Dokumentationen festgehalten, bestehend aus vollständig transkribierten und übersetzten Videoaufnahmen einer repräsentativen Auswahl aller wichtigen Typen von kommunikativen Ereignissen. Wir haben auch alte Witotoaufnahmen von rituellen Diskursen, die heute nicht mehr praktiziert werden, bearbeitet und in die Dokumentation integriert. Darüber hinaus wurden umfangreiche Daten der moribunden Sprache Resígaro, die jetzt nur noch zwei Sprecher hat, gesammelt. Wir haben auch umfangreiche Daten der inzwischen ausgestorbenen Nonuyasprache aus den 1970er bis 1990er Jahren vollständig bearbeitet und in das Korpus integriert.

Das Korpus besteht aus über 2000 einzelnen Aufnahmen mit insgesamt über 370 Stunden Länge. Alle Aufnahme sind thematisch sortiert im DOBES-Archiv abgelegt und mit Metadatenbeschreibungen versehen, die über den Inhalt, Teilnehmer, etc. Auskunft geben. Fast 700 dieser Aufnahmen sind transkribiert und ins Spanische übersetzt, das ergibt ein elektronisch online durchsuchbares Korpus von über 230.000 Wörtern. Darüber hinaus haben wir einen umfangreichen Anhang (ca. 180 Seiten) erstellt, der wichtige Informationen über die Sprachen und Kulturen der People of the Center enthält und die weiteren Verwendung der Daten auch durch Wissenschaftler, die nicht damit nicht vertraut sind, ermöglicht.

Wir haben auch speziell Daten für eine Vielzahl möglicher Analysen (anthropologische, linguistische, psycholinguistische und ethnobotanische- und zoologische) gesammelt und haben bereits selbst Analysen durchgeführt in Bezug auf linguistische Anthropologie, grammatische Beschreibung sowie historische Linguistik und Kontaktlinguistik. Aus unseren Daten haben wir auch Materialien speziell für die Sprachrevitalisierung erstellt, darunter Lehrmaterialien und 56 DVDs mit zweisprachigen Untertiteln. Ein Sprachdokumentationsserver wurde in Iquitos, Peru, installiert, der eine Kopie unserer Dokumentation enthält. Er stellt ein neues Zentrum für Sprachdokumentation dar, und ist Teil eines von uns mitbegründeten lateinamerikanischen Netzwerks.

Eine im Rahmen des Projekts angefertigte Dissertation, eine Referenzgrammatik des Ocaina, steht kurz vor dem Abschluss. Durch Lehrtätigkeiten haben wir auch dazu beigetragen, Sprachdokumentation an deutschen Hochschulen zu etablieren. Eine Reihe von Folgeprojekten und -aktivitäten, sowohl in Lateinamerika als auch Europa, beschäftigen sich unter anderem mit der Ausarbeitung weiterer Unterrichtsmaterialien und typologischen Studien anhand von Sprachdokumentationskorpora.

Report on the scientific results

The major result of the project is a large corpus of annotated primary data (§1), which is accompanied by a set of descriptive documents (§2), and which has led to a number of analytic outcomes (§3) and community materials and activities (§4).

1. Corpus of primary data

The project has produced a comprehensive corpus of primary data, providing a representative documentation of the linguistic and cultural practices of the People of the Center, which is processed and presented for multiple uses and scientific analyses. The corpus consists of a total of 180 hours of video recordings and about 190 hours audio-only recordings. These are organized into over 2,000 individual recording sessions, each described with IMDI Metadata descriptions, which specify the actors involved, place and time of recording, contents, etc. All sessions, including the transcription and translation files, are uploaded under a thematic node in the DOBES corpus tree, where they are accessible (in part on request) and electronically searchable. The documentation includes substantial documentations of five languages, numerous dialectal varieties, and recordings in about 15 locations in Peru and Colombia. More than 50 native speakers contributed substantial data. Through the inclusion of old data from as early as from 1913, the documentation spans almost a century of linguistic history of the People of the Center.

The content of the corpus is summarized in the following table. The number of transcribed and translated sessions is a subset of the total number of sessions. The number of time-aligned sessions is the subset of transcribed and translated sessions, whose annotation is viewable together with the video or audio recording (e.g. as subtitles) in the ELAN software. The remaining transcribed and translated sessions are in the Toolbox format and thus also electronically searchable.

<u>language</u>	<u>total number of sessions</u>	<u>number of transcribed and translated sessions</u>	<u>number of time-aligned sessions (in ELAN)</u>	<u>approx. number of transcribed words</u>
Bora	659	335	329	90,000
Witoto	239	119	21	92,000
Nonuya	121	118	118	21,000
Ocaina	729	48	46	12,000
Resígaro	256	75	75	17,000
Total	2,004	695	589	232,000

This corpus is a representative documentation of the linguistic diversity of the seven languages of the People of the Center: Witoto, Ocaina, and Nonuya belong to the Witotoan branch of the Witotoan family, Bora to the (distantly if at all related) Boran branch. Resígaro is an unrelated Arawakan language. The only two languages of the People of the Center not covered are Muinane (closely related to Bora) and the unclassified language Andoke, which has been previously documented. The coverage for each language is as broad as the vitality of each language permits. For the relatively vital Bora (approx. 2,000 speakers), Witoto (approx. 3,000 speakers), and Ocaina (approx. 50 speakers) extensive new data were collected, and older data were processed and integrated into the corpus (especially for Witoto). For Resígaro, as much and as varied data as possible were collected from the remaining three native speakers (two by the end of the project), in addition to data from semi-speakers. The documentation of Nonuya consists mostly of recordings made in the 1970s to 1990s with the last three fully competent speakers, who are now deceased or missing. These were processed with the help of a young Nonuya semi-speaker.

The documentation covers a variety of speech events and situations, including systematically sampled examples of formal genres (songs, myths, spells, narratives, etc.) as well as relatively informal events (drinking contests, hunting trips, etc.), and crucially also includes substantial documentation of multi-participant conversation for each of the living languages. Included are traditional events (festivals, healing rituals, etc.) and modern practice (folkloric performances for tourists, bilingual education in school, modern sport events, etc.). The following are a few examples of subsections of the corpus, illustrating the variety of data:

- a comprehensive and systematic documentation of Witoto ritual knowledge, covering various dialects and recordings since 1969
- 82 recordings of Witoto songs collected in 1913 by K. T. Preuss
- elicitation sessions on various aspects of grammatical structures, e.g. tone systems, possession, argument structure, negation
- especially designed experiments to investigate frames of spatial reference and the cognitive effects of shape-based linguistic classification systems
- documentations of traditional knowledge such as trap-making, fishing with poison, production of natural dyes and pottery, especially for Ocaina
- a comprehensive and systematic documentation of the elaborate Bora drum communication system (about 200 sessions) and of the more limited systems of Witoto and Ocaina
- documentations of medicinal plants and animal names (mammals, reptiles, birds), with Latin species names and photographs
- palatography for Bora vowels

2. Descriptive documents

The corpus of primary data is accompanied by a set of introductory descriptive documents (an “apparatus”) that ensures long-term accessibility of its contents. These documents provide the background information that is necessary to fully appreciate and analyze the primary data for anyone who is not familiar with the languages and culture of the People of the Centre. The information provided in these documents is relevant to the entire corpus and thus complements the information given for each session in its IMDI metadata description. These documents, as given in the following table, are also uploaded and publicly accessible in PDF format within the DOBES corpus tree. They cover the historical, geographic, and natural environment, as well as extensive introductions to the ethnographic context (material culture and society). For each language, there are grammar sketches, including explanations on the orthographies used in transcriptions. The grammar sketches in particular are at the same time analytic outcomes of the project (see next section).

<u>title of document</u>	<u>authors</u>	<u>pages</u>
Geography, history, and natural environment, including maps	F. Seifart, P. v. Hildebrandt	7
Material culture of the People of the Center	J. Gasché	25
The society of the People of the Center	J. Gasché	41
Genetic and areal relations between the languages of the People of the Center	F. Seifart, D. Fagua	2
Introduction to the grammar of Bora	F. Seifart	18
Orthography and some grammatical features of Resígaro	F. Seifart	4
Introduction to the grammar of Ocaina	D. Fagua	14
Grammatical sketch of Witoto	J. Gasché	59
Glossary of terms in regional Spanish		3
Bibliography		6
Total pages		179

3. Analytic outcomes

The collected data have been subject to a number of analyses by project members, in some cases in cooperation with others. These analyses are only a small fraction of the possible analyses for which specific data have already been collected. So far we carried out analyses relating mainly to linguistic anthropology, grammatical description, and historical and contact linguistics.

Outcomes relating to linguistic anthropology include an analysis of Witoto riddles (Gasché 2008; see the list of publications in the tabular part, further below, for references), and an analysis of a new Witoto genre (Gasché’s 2008b conference presentation), as well as Gasché’s 25+41-page ethnographic introduction to the

linguistic practices of the People of the Centre published online as part of the current documentation (see above).

A major analytic outcome of the project is the grammatical description of Ocaina, a to date practically undescribed language, in Doris Fagua's doctoral dissertation (to be handed in in 2010), selected aspects of which are published in Fagua & Seifart (forthcoming). We described Witoto grammar in Gasché's 59-page grammar of Witoto, which is published as a descriptive document in the present documentation. Further analyses of grammatical structures include the finalization of a comparative study of nominal classification in Witotoan languages (Seifart 2007; Seifart & Payne 2007; Seifart & Payne, eds. 2007), an analysis of sentence connectors in Bora narratives (Seifart forthcoming), and of valency increasing morphology in Resígaro (Seifart's accepted conference presentation for 2010). An analysis of valency classes in Bora by Seifart for an edited volume by Malchukov et al. is currently in preparation.

Bora drum communication is analyzed with respect to prosodic typology in Seifart and Meyer (accepted conference presentation for 2010). Seifart and Fagua, with Perniss et al. (2008 conference presentation) analyzed the influence on non-linguistic cognition of the shape-based Bora nominal classification system, in comparison to local Spanish (non-Bora speakers), British sign language and spoken English.

Resígaro data have been analyzed extensively with respect to the massive contact-induced changes under Bora influence (Seifart's 2007c and Steinkrüger and Seifart's 2009 conference presentations). These studies are based on quantitative analyses of the distribution of Bora elements in the entire corpus of Resígaro data. The results are potentially a substantial contribution to the theory of borrowability of linguistic items.

We use the extensive lexical data collected in this project for a re-evaluation of the Witotoan linguistic family, taking into account for the first time Nonuya data (Seifart's 2009 conference presentation; Seifart & Echeverri in preparation). This shows that Nonuya is a sister language to Ocaina and also related to Witoto, but that the genetic link between these three languages and Bora (and Muinane) is still doubtful.

In addition, project members contributed to documentary linguistics and language revitalization methodology. Seifart (2008) and Gasché & Seifart (2009) focus on the identification and selection of speech events to be included in a representative language documentation and their organization in hierarchical corpus tree structures. Seifart et al. (2009) discuss the emerging network of regional language archives in South America. Gasché developed a new methodology for teaching endangered languages as a second language in schools of communities that are at an advanced stage of languages shift (García & Gasché 2008, vol. 2). Project work was also relevant for a scientific

contribution to the development of orthographies for endangered languages, in particular in the context of documentation projects (Seifart 2006).

4. Community materials and activities

Language documentation has been carried out with the consent and active involvement of the speech communities. Accordingly, we have taken measures to make the relevant data and other outcomes at all times accessible to the speech community, in particular in view of the fact that these do not have internet access. For this reason we created a range of materials from the audio and video recordings and annotations (see §1, above). A video DVD and an audio CD library was produced with colored booklets for each DVD and CD that specifies its contents. This library consists of 56 video DVDs, each containing a collection of thematically related recordings that have bilingual subtitles in Spanish and the respective indigenous language, and menus for navigation and choosing subtitle languages, and 60 Audio CDs, mostly documenting traditional songs performed at festivals. Transcriptions and translations were additionally printed and bound into volumes, each volume including all contributions by one informant. In principle, each contributor has received copies of the sessions he or she participated in as an informant, both as a video DVD (or audio CD) and as a printout of the transcription and translation, except for recordings of little value to the speakers, e.g. elicitation of grammatical structures.

In addition, we deposited computers (and the solar panels used in fieldwork for power supply) in the three main fieldwork sites in Peru with copies of video and audio recordings and annotation files and trained local speakers to access these.

We also created a number of materials specifically for language revitalization purposes, based on data collected in the project. García & Gasché (2008) consists of one volume containing an edited Witoto text with Spanish translations and illustrations by a Witoto painter, accompanied by a CD with the recording of the Witoto text. A second volume contains lexical and grammatical explanations to each sentence in the text, specifically geared towards teaching Witoto as a second language in the community schools. Gasché's grammar of Witoto (published as descriptive document in this documentation) is also written in a style accessible to indigenous language teachers. The use of these materials was taught in specific workshops for Witoto teachers.

Doris Fagua developed teaching materials in collaboration with Ocaina speakers, consisting of six units, each covering an aspect of Ocaina grammatical structure (Siake et al. 2008). A traditional Bora narrative was edited and published as a bilingual text, of which 150 bound copies were distributed in Bora schools (Vega et al. 2009). The transcription and translations of the complete collection of songs pertaining to one important Bora festival cycle were printed and bound in an about 1000-pages volume (Trigoso and Gasché 2009), which is currently

being revised by native speakers for publication and distribution in the speech communities. Most Nonuya data were formatted and printed in a 200-page volume, which was given to the (descendants of the) Nonuya community, together with copies on CD of the data processed in the context of the project.

Project members taught a number of workshops for teachers in Bora, Ocaina, and Witoto communities in Peru and Colombia (see tabular part below).

Self-evaluation in comparison with the original objectives and working plan

The primary objective of this project was to compile and fully process a large and varied corpus of primary data, which representatively documents the cultural and linguistic practices of the People of the Centre. We believe that the People of the Center corpus (see above) meets this objective most satisfactorily.

Frank Seifart and Doris Fagua took up positions during the project, which was necessary for their mid-term professional career planning. Therefore the project activities had to be adjusted at various points, deviating from the original plan, mostly with respect to timing. Doris Fagua received a PhD grant from the University 7 in Paris in early 2005, shortly after the beginning of the project. After that she did not receive a salary from the project, as originally planned, but agreed to nevertheless collect and process Ocaina data for the documentation project. In October 2007, Seifart took up a position at the Universität Regensburg, which reduced the time he had available for project work. We are grateful to the Volkswagen Foundation for having agreed to employing additional assistants and to overall extend the project duration (from originally three years to almost five years), which allowed us to successfully complete our objectives under the new circumstances.

We carried out a number of additional activities, with the kind consent of the Volkswagen Foundation. We were able to more actively involve Juan Alvaro Echeverri in the project, which has led to a much more comprehensive documentation of the Nonuya language than foreseen in the application. We also had the opportunity to support the restoration of the oldest existing audio recordings of the People of the Center, K.T. Preuss' Witoto wax cylinders from 1913, at the Ethnologisches Museum Berlin. Digital versions of these recordings were integrated in the corpus. We did not include in the original proposal fieldwork in Colombia, where languages of the People of Center are also spoken, because of the unstable political situation. By the beginning of the project, however, the situation had become stable and safe, so we could undertake fieldwork in various locations in Colombia, documenting additional dialects and genres not found in Peru.

In addition to the huge amount of data that are uploaded and accessible at this point (see above), we collected and processed to some degree an additional

considerable amount of material that is not uploaded yet. The work schemes for data processing developed in the project will allow us to continuously process and eventually upload further data. Particularly important in this respect is Jürg Gasché's commitment to continue documentation work with the help of assistants employed by himself in Iquitos since the finalization of the project.

The extent to which we were able to carry out networking and diffusion of language documentation methods and technology in Latin American was also not foreseen. An important measure in this context was the installation of the language documentation server in Iquitos, through an agreement between the MPI Nijmegen and the IIAP.

In some respects, however, our results are somewhat more modest than expected. The strong focus on documentation in form of a large corpus of primary data has led to a somewhat lesser than expected depth of analysis of these data in the context of the project. We successfully processed a large amount of data to a point from where further analysis can easily be done, in particular by a large amount of carefully checked transcriptions and translations. The amount of interlinear morpheme glosses and lexical databases is, however, at this point limited. We did create and test setups in the Toolbox software that allow to relatively easily produce these from the available data. We were also not able to actively involve native speakers quite to the extent that we had hoped for. An important reason for this is that it proved difficult to leave equipment in the communities, which would have been used by native speakers to collect and process data in the absence of project members. Also, Doris Fagua's PhD dissertation is not finished, as we had planned. For the proposed task (a reference grammar of Ocaina), the current time frame (a total of five years) is, however, still reasonable, in particular given Doris Fagua's substantial contributions to the language documentation project during those years.

Added value gained through interdisciplinary and international cooperation

Our project strongly benefited from the joint linguistic and anthropological expertise of the project members. Beyond that, we engaged in interdisciplinary cooperation with specialists in cognitive science (Perniss et al.'s conference presentation 2008), emulated speech systems (Seifart and Meyer's accepted conference presentation 2010), and electronic network technology (Trilsbeek et al.'s conference presentation 2007), among others.

We closely cooperate with academic communities in Europe, in particular with the following countries: France (CELIA-CNRS Paris, DDL-CNRS Lyon), Great Britain (SOAS, London), The Netherlands (MPI Nijmegen), and Germany (Regensburg, MPI Leipzig, etc.). We also engaged in close cooperate with academic communities in South America, e.g. Peru (IIAP Iquitos, UNMSM Lima), Colombia (UN and CCELA Bogotá and Leticia), Brazil (Mueso Goeldi Belém,

etc.), and Argentina (UBN and CONICET Buenos Aires). The regional network of language documentation servers in these countries (Seifart et al. 2008) has led to further cooperations and exchanges. We are also part of the academic network DELAMAN.

Frank Seifart and Doris Fagua contributed Ocaina and Bora data to the “Counting Concepts and Numeral Systems Project” by Eugene Chan and Bernard Comrie. They also contributed to the UNESCO (Interactive) Atlas of the World’s Languages in Danger up-to-date information about Ocaina and Bora (see <http://www.unesco.org/culture/en/endangeredlanguages/atlas>).

Future perspectives and sustainability of the project

Partially on the basis of his experience as coordinator of a DOBES project, Seifart was appointed a (non-tenured) assistant professor position at the Universität Regensburg in 2007 and a Senior Staff Member position at the Max-Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology in Leipzig in August 2009, where he will continue to analyze data collected in the documentation project for the following five years. There he will apply together with colleagues for a project called “Typocorp”, in which language documentation corpora will be used for typological studies.

The language documentation server installed at the IIAP in Iquitos will be a lasting center for socio-cultural and linguistic documentation of the Peruvian Amazon, inviting new (and old) projects to contribute data. It is also an important reference for the integration into larger Latin American and worldwide electronic infrastructure networks (Alice2, CLARA, CLARIN, etc.), which facilitates the exchange and training of Latin American scientists. As a consequence also of the participation in the DOBES project, the IIAP in Iquitos has launched a special program on social diversity that includes linguistic research. Our projects also had an impact on other local Peruvian institutions which have put indigenous languages on their agendas, e.g. in developing curricula for public schools.

Doris Fagua has written up a proposal for a follow-up project to develop Ocaina educational material based on data collected in the project, which will include primers about, e.g., traditional pottery and basketry. We substantially trained a number of speakers of all five languages in documentation work, in particular in transcription and translation. These speakers will continue to document their language and are eager to participate in future projects.

Frank Seifart helped to establish language documentation at German universities and encouraged the use of language documentation resources by students through teaching the following courses:

Ruhr-Universität Bochum: *Strukturkurs Bora-Miraña* (Mar. - July 2006);

Humboldt Universität Berlin: *Amazonassprachen* (October 2006 - February 2007);

Universität Regensburg: *Einführung in die Sprachdokumentation* (Mar. - July 2008), *Einführung in die Struktur einer nicht-indogermanischen Sprache I & II: Bora* (Oct. 2008 - Feb. 2009 & Mar. - July 2009), *Methoden der Sprachdokumentation* (Mar. - July 2009).

Contribution to the specific aims of the funding initiative

Our project has contributed exemplary and comprehensive documentations of five severely endangered languages, providing a lasting, well-organized corpus of primary data for analyses in a variety of scientific disciplines as well as for language maintenance activities. We disseminated DOBES language documentation methods and technology in Latin America and helped to establish language documentation in German universities. We contributed to the development of the DOBES programme by active participation in various DOBES committees (steering committee, ad-hoc committee for strategic planning of software development) and made specific proposals to a central problem of language documentation, the organization of recording sessions in a hierarchical corpus tree (Gasché & Seifart 2008).

Public relation activities and resonance in the media

Presentation by Doris Fagua about “*Échantillon de la documentation de la langue ocaina*”, on the occasion of Fête de la Science, Espace Jussieu, Université Paris 7, Denis Diderot, Oct. 2005

Presentation by Doris Fagua about “Documentation des langues menacées. L'exemple de l'ocaina (Uitoto) en Amazonie Nor-Occidentale”, on the occasion of 'Linguistique de Terrain', Licence de linguistique, Université Paris 7, Denis Diderot, campus Jussieu, Feb. 2007

Three appearances of Jürg Gasché in local Iquitos television on the occasion of the publication of García & Gasché (2008) (June 2008)

One appearances of Jürg Gasché in local Iquitos television about the DOBES documentation project (April 2009)

Various newspaper reports in the Iquitos press on the occasion of the signing the agreement and installation of the language documentation server at the IIAP in Iquitos (Oct. 2005)

Appearance on RBB radio (Berlin) of Frank Seifart on the occasion of the annual meeting of the German Association for Endangered Languages (Nov. 2006)

Further aspects

Although the cooperation with the technical team in Nijmegen was overall very good, in some cases, the processing of data in Nijmegen proved to be a bottleneck in our work scheme. We probably could have processed even more data if more manpower had been available at the technical team in Nijmegen to carry out the data processing steps that can only be done there, not by individual teams.

Our project has substantially benefitted from various adjustments to the original proposal, made in accordance with the Volkswagen Foundation, when mid-term career planning made new planning necessary (Fagua's and Seifart's appointments) and unforeseen opportunities to collect and process additional valuable data arose, e.g. through field work in Colombia and the restoration of wax cylinder recordings.

Tabular part of the report

Participating researchers and students, separated by institution and funding source

	<u>Institutional affiliation</u>	<u>DOBES funding</u>
Frank Seifart, principal investigator	09/04-05/07 U. Bochum	half time employment
	06/07-09/07 U. Bochum	full time employment
	10/07-07/09 U. Regensburg	regular travel etc. reimbursements
Doris Fagua, PhD student	09/04-12/04 U. Bochum	half time employment
	01/05-12/08 U. 7 Paris	regular travel etc. reimbursements
	01/09-07/09 IIAP Iquitos	regular per diems, travel etc. reimbursements
Jürg Gasché, investigator	09/04-07/09 IIAP, Iquitos	regular travel etc. reimbursements
Juan Alvaro Echeverri, investigator	03/07-07/09 U. Nacional de Colombia	regular travel etc. reimbursements
Nikolaus Himmelmann, advisor	09/04-09/07 U. Bochum	none
	10/07-07/09 U. Münster	none

Additional cooperation partners in the project (not applicants)

Assistants employed on a regular basis:

Native speaker assistants: Rosa Andrade, Rogelio Andrade Nuñez, Pablo Andrade Ocagane, Santiago Cubicaje, Celia Díaz, Felipe Flores Andrade, Alfonso Garcia, Manuel Ruiz Miveco, Fernando Montes Tuesta, Clever Panduro, Clever Rodriguez, Manuel Trigoso, René Vásquez, Ernesto Tello, Zacarias Mibeco

Additional assistants in Iquitos: Nandier Meza, Joilé Villanueva

Additional assistant in Bogotá: Edilamar Bustos

Ruhr-Universität Bochum: Jan Strunk, Victoria Rodrigues, Judith Köhne, Rahel Beyer, Iva Renic

Universität Regensburg: Katharina Höhendinger, Melissa Houser, Dominik Messer, Susanne Naimer, Katharina Knuffmann, Nicole Goltz, Vanessa Messer, Florian Greiner, Michael Fischbach

Institutional cooperation partners:

Ruhr-Universität Bochum: administrative staff and Dr. Martin Hölter

Universität Regensburg: administrative staff and Prof. Dr. Johannes Helmbrecht

IIAP (Iquitos): Dr. Luis Campos Baca, Econ. Hernán Tello, Ing. Victor Miyakawa

MPI Nijmegen: Paul Trilsbeek, Peter Wittenburg

DELAMAN (digital endangered languages and musics archive network)

Museu do Indio (Brazil)

Universidad de Buenos Aires, CONICET (Argentina)

Ethnologisches Museum Berlin

Universidad Nacional de Colombia

FECONA (association of indigenous communities of the Ampiyacu river, Peru)

Theses written in the course of the project

Doris Fagua's dissertation on morphosyntactic aspects of Ocaina will be handed in in 2010

Publications

Note that texts published as part of the documentation, under the node "descriptive documents" (see section 2 of the *Report on the scientific results*, above), are not included in the following list.

Articles:

Fagua, Doris, and Frank Seifart. Forthcoming in 2010. Aspectos morfosintácticos del ocaina: entre rasgos genéticos (familia Witoto) e influencias areales. Accepted for publication in *Mundos Amazónicos*, peer-reviewed online journal of the Universidad Nacional de Colombia.

- Gasché, Jürg. 2008. Cuatro cantos-adivanzas huitoto. *Folia Amazónica* 16, no. 1-2: 89-100.
- Gasché, Jürg, and Frank Seifart. 2009. Towards a shared classificatory tree for DOBES language documentations. Manuscript.
- Seifart, Frank. 2006. Orthography development. In *Essentials of language documentation*, ed. by J. Gippert, N. Himmelmann and U. Mosel. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter. 275-299.
- Seifart, Frank. 2007. The prehistory of nominal classification in Witotoan languages. *International Journal of American Linguistics* 73, no. 4: 411-445.
- Seifart, Frank. 2008. On the representativeness of language documentations. In *Language Documentation and Description, Vol. 5*, ed. Peter K. Austin. 60-76. London: SOAS.
- Seifart, Frank. 2009a. Pronombres de forma. El uso anafórico de marcas de clases en miraña. *Forma y Función* 22. 69-96.
- Seifart, Frank. 2009b. Multidimensional typology and Miraña class markers. In *New Challenges in Typology. Transcending the Borders and Refining the Distinctions*, ed. Patience Epps and Alexandre Arhipov, 365-385. Trends in Linguistics. Studies and Monographs 127. Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Seifart, Frank. Forthcoming. The Bora connector pronoun and tail-head linkage: a study in language-specific grammaticalization. *Linguistics*.
- Seifart, Frank. Submitted. Towards a typology of unitization: Miraña noun classes compared to numeral classifiers and singulatives.
- Seifart, Frank, and Doris L. Payne. 2007. Nominal classification in the North West Amazon: Issues in areal diffusion and typological characterization. *International Journal of American Linguistics* 73, no. 4: 381-387.
- Seifart, Frank, and Juan Alvaro Echeverri. In preparation. Towards a re-evaluation of the Witotoan linguistic family (North West Amazon).
- Seifart, Frank, Sebastian Drude, Bruna Franchetto, Jürg Gasché, Lucía Golluscio, and Elizabeth Manrique. 2008. Language Documentation and Archives in South America. *Language Documentation & Conservation* 2, no. 1: 130-140.

Books

- García Vega, Alfonso, and Jorge Gasché. 2008. *Ñekirofe lletarafue – El consejo de la chambira, vol. 1: Texto en lengua huitoto (dialecto buue) y traducción al castellano, vol 2: anotaciones lexicales y gramaticales al texto huitoto (dialecto buue)*. Iquitos: IIAP. [Witoto text and teaching material]
- Siake, Noé, Simeón Siake & Doris Fagua. 2008. *lvohsahfo xafoi. Cartilla del idioma Okaina uvóhsa*. La Chorrera (Colombia): Manuscript. [Teaching material for the Ocaina variety spoken in Colombia]

Siake, Noé, Simeón Siake, Fernando Montes & Doris Fagua. 2008. *Uvóóhsa foou, xafoou. Nahaxonimó agodyudsa tyohoovu*. Iquitos (Peru): Manuscript. [Teaching material for the Ocaina variety spoken in Peru]

Editions

Seifart, Frank, and Doris L. Payne, eds. 2007. *Nominal Classification in the North West Amazon* [=special issue of the *International Journal of American Linguistics*]. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Bound printouts of edited data collections:

Echeverri, Juan Alvaro (ed.) 2009. *Lengua nonuya. Transcripción y traducción de grabaciones de Mamerto Ríos (1973, 1991), Humberto Ayarce (1994-1996), Rafael Grande (1996-1997), Margarita Kapojó (2007)*. Comunidad indígena de Peña Roja: Proyecto DoBes "Gente de Centro".

Trigoso, Manuel (interpreter) & Jürg Gasché (compiler). 2008. *Apújko másjjúúne. Canciones de la fiesta apújco*. Iquitos (Peru): Manuscript. [Collection of about 500 traditional Bora songs, about 1000 pages]

Vega, Victoria, with the collaboration of Manuel Ruíz Mibeco, Frank Seifart, and Clever Panduro. 2009. *Méénujcátsi pívyve / El origen de las peleas. Texto en lengua bora y traducción al castellano*. Regensburg: DOBES/IIAP/Universität Regensburg.

Conference and workshop presentations (selection)

Fagua, Doris. 2006. "La predicación en Ocaina". Paper given at CNRS/DDL, Lyon. May

Fagua, Doris. 2008a. "Flexion et dérivation nominale et verbale en ocaina". PhD student-colloquium 'Flexion/dérivation' at CELIA-CNRS, Paris, November.

Fagua, Doris. 2008b. "Relations grammaticales en ocaina (encodage et opérations)". PhD student-colloquium 'Relations grammaticales' at CELIA-CNRS, Paris, March 2008.

Fagua, Doris. 2009a. "Nominalisations en ocaina". PhD student-colloquium 'La translation' at CELIA-CNRS, Paris, May

Fagua, Doris. 2009b. "El nominal en oc/kaina", Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Bogotá, February.

Fagua, Doris. 2009c. "Analyse morphosyntaxique de l'ocaina (Witoto), variété dialectale uvohsa". Poster presented at AERES, comisión de evaluación del CNRS, CELIA, Paris, February.

Fagua, Doris, and Frank Seifart. 2009. "Aspectos morfosintácticos del ocaina: entre rasgos genéticos (familia Witoto) e influencias areales". International Congress of Americanists, Mexico, D.F., July.

Gasché, Jürg. 2008a. "La educación intercultural indígena". Universidad de Buenos Aires, August.

- Gasché, Jürg. 2008b. "Como pasar del discurso oral al texto redactado en una lengua indígena. Problemas de creación de un estilo escrito en lengua indígena". Workshop of DOBES-Universidad de Buenos Aires Universidad de Buenos Aires, August.
- Perniss, Pamela, David P. Vinson, Gabriella Vigliocco, and Frank Seifart. 2008. "Modality vs. typology effects: Investigating the divide". Poster presented at the 14th Annual Conference on Architectures and Mechanisms for Language Processing, Cambridge, UK, September.
- Seifart, Frank. 2005a. "Documenting Amazonian Languages". Paper given at Georgia Southern University, Statesboro, Georgia. September.
- Seifart, Frank. 2005b. "Orthography development for endangered languages". Paper given at ELAP Workshop: Endangered Languages and Literacy, SOAS, London. December.
- Seifart, Frank. 2006a. "Contact-induced change in Resígaro (Arawak) under influence from Bora (Witotoan)". Paper given at CNRS/DDDL, Lyon. May.
- Seifart, Frank. 2006b. "Sampling in language documentation". Paper given at DOBES Workshop, Nijmegen. June.
- Seifart, Frank. 2006c. "The role of systematic sampling procedures in language documentation". Paper given at SOAS/ELDP Workshop.
- Seifart, Frank. 2007a. "Discourse particles and discourse-structuring mechanisms in Bora and Resígaro". Paper given at the Workshop on Discourse markers in Amerindian Languages. ACLC/University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam. December.
- Seifart, Frank. 2007b. "Documentation practice in the North West Amazon: Local, Regional and International Perspectives". Paper given at the International Symposium Perspectives from Linguistic and Cultural documentation: Ethics and collaborative research. Universidad de Buenos Aires - Museo Etnográfico, Buenos Aires. October.
- Seifart, Frank. 2007c. "Restructuring nominal grammar only: Bora influence on Resígaro (North West Amazon)". Paper given at Language contact and morphosyntactic variation and change, Paris. September.
- Seifart, Frank. 2008. "Die Dokumentation sprachlicher und kultureller Praktiken im Amazonasgebiet". Paper given at Forschungskolloquium Philologien, Universität Regensburg, June.
- Seifart, Frank. 2009. Towards a re-evaluation of the Witotoan linguistic family. Paper presented at Max Planck Institute for evolutionary Anthropology, November.
- Seifart, Frank. Accepted for 2010. "Valency increasing morphology in Resígaro". International conference 'Amazonicas III'. Bogotá, April.
- Seifart, Frank, and Julien Meyer. Accepted for 2010. "Bora drum communication: What the study of emulated speech systems contributes to prosodic typology". Paper accepted for the symposium "Prosodic Typology: State of the Art and Future Prospects" at the 32nd Annual Conference of the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Sprachwissenschaft (DGfS), Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, February.

- Seifart, Frank, and Patrick O. Steinkrüger. 2009. "Transfer of derivational morphology without borrowing of stems: Resígaro (Arawakan, Peru) and Chabacano (Creole, Philippines)". Paper given at Morphologies in Contact, Universität Bremen, October.
- Seifart, Frank, Sebastian Drude, Bruna Franchetto, Jürg Gasché, Lucía Golluscio, and Elizabeth Manrique. 2007. "Language documentation and archives in South America". Paper given at the DELAMAN annual meeting, Mexico. November.
- Trilsbeek, Paul, Sebastian Drude, Bruna Franchetto, Jürg Gasche, Lucia Golluscio, Carlos Levinho, Victor Miyakawa, Frank Seifart, Daan Broeder, and Peter Wittenburg. 2007. "Repositories and Archives as Nodes in a Grid". Paper given at the DELAMAN annual meeting, Mexico. November.

Specific events, e.g. workshops

Workshops organized and taught by project members relating to the diffusion of language documentation methods and technology at South American universities and research institutions:

Métodos y tecnologías de la documentación lingüística. Two-day workshop taught at Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos, Lima, Peru (Sep. 2006) (Seifart, Gasché, Fagua, Trilsbeek, Drude, Wittenburg)

Métodos y tecnologías de la documentación lingüística. Two-day workshop taught at Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Bogotá (Feb. 2007) (Seifart, Echeverri)

Metodología de la investigación lingüística, tendencias actuales: documentación lingüística, Maestría de Lingüística, Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Bogotá (Mar. 2005) (Fagua)

Presentación e introducción al uso de herramientas para la documentación lingüística (Imdi, Elan, Toolbox), Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Bogotá (Mar. 2005) (Fagua)

Introducción a Imdi, Taller Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Bogotá (June 2009) (Fagua)

Introducción a Imdi y Elan, herramientas para la documentación lingüística, Workshop for antropologists and linguists working in the Peruvian Amazon. IIAP, Iquitos (Sep. 2009) (Fagua)

Workshops organized and taught by project members relating to the diffusion of project results and language maintenance in indigenous communities:

Taller de capacitación sobre gramática witoto y el uso de las cartillas para 34 maestros witoto del Putumayo, Napo y Nanay, en coordinación con la Dirección Regional de Educación de Loreto (DREL), Iquitos, (Apr. 2008) (Gasché)

Taller de capacitación sobre gramática witoto y el uso de las cartillas para 11 maestros witoto del Ampiyacu y Bajo Amazonas, en coordinación con la Dirección Regional de Educación de Loreto (DREL), Pucaurquillo (Ampiyacu), (Sep.-Oct. 2009) (Gasché)

Documentación y elaboración de material didáctico en ocaina, La Chorrera, Colombia (May 2008) (Fagua)

Five-day workshop for Bora and Witoto teachers about Witoto and Bora grammar for primary schools at La Chorrera (Colombia) (Mar. 2007) (Gasché, Seifart)